
Deliverable D-JIP2-3.6

Knowledge transfer and dissemination

Workpackage: 3

Cohesive Task 3.4

Responsible Partner: SVA, APHA

Contributing partners: ISS, RIVM, INIAV,
WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER AND DISSEMINATION

Exchange of information on low-threshold signals of zoonotic events within and between countries in Europe

1. Background

The aim of this task was to enhance informal exchange of signals of events or trends of zoonoses that are either not notifiable or occurring in animal species traditionally not in focus of the authorities. Currently, information on larger outbreaks of notifiable or unknown agents in food-producing animals is either communicated via the OIE or via the Commission. ECDC has created platforms for information sharing on food- and waterborne infections and vector-borne infections in humans. EFSA has networks for animal diseases, microbiological risks and zoonoses. These networks are not fully operating in a One Health manner. Also, information on non-notifiable diseases, smaller events or trends are not naturally shared within the existing EU platforms. Therefore, the aim of this task was to find ways of sharing experiences on zoonotic events between countries, across sectors and disciplines but not to replace the current formal ways of information sharing or notification.

2. Workshops on information sharing

According to the application the task was to be performed during the last year of the project and build on experiences gathered within the previous tasks. Instead of building a new platform the participating institutes APHA, RIVM and SVA decided to organise a digital workshop and invite COHESIVE participants and other persons with an interest in this way of sharing experiences. After the first invitation the organisers received suggestions of issues to be raised. The first workshop was intended to be held in December 2020. This needed to be postponed to February 2021 due to a large outbreak of avian influenza and the key persons being heavily involved in the outbreak management.

On February 3, 2021, a 2.5 h workshop was organised via Microsoft Teams. A total of 21 persons from eight countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Sweden, United Kingdom) participated in the workshop. Three topics were discussed in the workshop: an increase of food-borne cryptosporidiosis, monitoring of antimicrobial resistance and increase of incidents of *Brucella canis* in dogs. The workshop clearly showed a need for further activities on brucellosis in dogs since several of the participants were clearly facing the same challenges. The workshop participants received minutes of the workshop as well as copies of the presentations. Minutes are included as an appendix of this report.

The COHESIVE collaborators contacted OH EJP IDEMBRU to discuss further collaborations on this field. COHESIVE and IDEMBRU participants decided to organize a specific digital workshop on brucellosis in dogs. Prior to the workshop, IDEMBRU and COHESIVE participants created an online survey with questions on analytical methods, notification status, surveillance, for instance and sent it to the NRL *Brucella* contact persons as well as to other *Brucella* reference laboratories. The 3 h workshop organized on May 18, 2021 via Microsoft Teams, was open to all persons interested in the subject. First invitation to the workshop was sent on April 7, 2021 to COHESIVE, IDEMBRU participants. The EJP communication team aided in spreading information and everyone was allowed to forward the invitation to other persons with an interest in the subject. All persons interested to attend the workshop were asked to register.

At the workshop presentations were given on prevalence, diagnostic aspects, outbreak investigations and control measures applied (Appendix 2). The workshop attracted over 170 participants from a range of countries within and outside Europe. The participants represented many different disciplines from different sectors (epidemiologists, diagnostic experts, risk assessors, operational risk managers, bacteriologists, food safety experts). The workshop was considered very fruitful. The workshop participants received minutes of the workshop and copies of the presentations.

IDEMBRU and COHESIVE have continued co-operation and are summarising the outputs of the workshop and establishing clear data-gaps for continued international collaboration in this area. IDEMBRU, COHESIVE with some other partners, such as the University of Nantes and Bristol, are currently preparing a scientific manuscript on the results.

A third digital workshop was organised on December 15, 2021, using the same platform of Microsoft Teams. In this workshop zoonotic risks of *Salmonella* and Hantavirus in pet rats and feeder rats were discussed among the 30 participants as well as the risk of introduction of Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever via ticks of *Hyalomma* species. Minutes of the workshop were circulated at the end of December 2021.

3. Impact

The task 3.4 fulfilled the aim of enhancing the exchange of signals across sectors and countries. For this, an informal international group has been set up with Terms of Reference, which will continue to meet after the project ends. The first workshop on sharing signals showed that many countries experienced similar kind of issues around *Brucella canis*, indicating the added value of such exchange of information between countries. Within the task no platform for tools developed in the other tasks was created, as indicated in the application, but the existing tools of MS Teams are used. The last workshop organised further confirmed the usefulness of the informal information sharing and the group intends to continue with the forum. The way of working of the group will be further refined along the way as holds also true for getting acknowledged for its added value by the One Health community.

The aim of the group is not to affect the existing systems of data exchange or notifications, but to provide a channel to raise issues that currently lack a cross-sectorial platform.

Appendix 1.

COHESIVE informal signal sharing meeting: kick-off and introduction

Location: MS Teams

Date: 03/02/2021

Time: 10:00 – 12:30 CET

Participants: Gaia Scavia, Sandra Cavaco, Trude Marie Lyngstad, Karin Nyberg, Charlotte Cook, Elina Lahti, Kitty Maasen, Johanne Ellis-Iversen, Cecilia Wolff, Eduardo Costa, Hannah Joan Jørgensen, Mats Lindblad, Gavin Watkins, Andrew Frost, John McGiven, Frits Vlaanderen, Ed Van Klink, Renáta Karpíšková, Ivana Kolackova, Rob Dewar, Zuzana Nordeng

1. Agenda

Name	Title	Time
Rob	Introduction & welcome, who am I	09:05
	Unlisted Attendees	09:10
Sandra	Who am I	09:13
Ed VK	Who am I	09:16
Kitty	Who am I	09:19
Mats	Who am I	09:22
	Cryptosporidium in Sweden	09:29
	Discussion	09:39
Karin	Who am I	09:42
Gavin	Who am I	09:45
Victor	Who am I	09:48
Hannah	Who am I	09:51
Joey	Who am I	09:54
	DANMAP	10:04
	Discussion	10:14
Break		10:21
Charlotte	Who am I	10:24
Eduardo	Who am I	10:27
Elina	Who am I	10:30
	Brucella canis	10:35
	Discussion	10:50

Cecilia	Who am I	10:53
Stefan	Who am I	10:56
Gaia	Who am I	10:59
Trude	Who am I	11:02
Zuzanna	Who am I	11:05
	Discussion	11:20

1.1. Notes

Mats Lindblad – *Cryptosporidium parvum* in leafy vegetables

- Cryptosporidium is a largely overlooked pathogen in the food sector.
- However cases in Sweden are increasing.
- Though it is a notifiable disease, there is no routine surveillance done on leafy vegetables.
- There has also been a general increase in number of foodborne outbreaks in Sweden since 2010.
- Authorities must work together to tackle the pathogen including:
 - **Public Health Agency of Sweden**
– surveillance and subtyping of human isolates
 - **Swedish Food Agency**
- coordination of foodborne outbreak investigations
 - **National Veterinary Institute**
- research and analyses
 - **County Medical Officers and Local Competent Food Authorities**
- food borne outbreak investigations
 - **County Veterinarians**
- competent authority for primary production
- Kale is a particular implicated food in Sweden as it is widely eaten at Christmas time.
- The source of infection from Cryptosporidium outbreaks thought to be from manure since water (irrigation) usually from deep wells free from Crypto. Also could be from wildlife and rodents.
- Cryptosporidium awareness has been increasing since 2 large outbreaks in 2010-2011.
- Additional information from questions:
 - Kale is primarily grown in Southern Sweden
 - Routine surveillance on water not done, and water safety is under jurisdiction of food safety in Sweden.
 - Causes of outbreaks still largely unknown

Johanne Ellis-Iversen – benefits of OH collaborations in understanding risks and signal sharing

- DANMAP integrated working surveillance program initiated in 1995.
- In Denmark collaboration is highly integrated along the disease detection pathway.
- There are annualised reports and these are put together by a collaborative working group throughout the year, ending in November with a seminar.
- Objectives are to follow trends over time and observe emergence of new antibiotic resistance
- Strong correlation between the consumption of antibiotics and AMR.
- Relationship between domestically acquired, food-acquired and travel associated cases of AMR which can only be seen through integrative approach.
- Can also see epidemiological changes in spread patterns.
- Allows alteration of methods to reduce AMR
- Work on AMR in Denmark is internationally accredited.
- Information from questions:

- Raised the issues of AMR from aquaculture.
- Noted that no representative from that field were present.
- Joey to send AMR aquaculture paper for sharing wider.

Elina Lahti

- International trade of dogs makes it difficult to prevent the spread of B.canis
- There have been several outbreaks in Sweden associated with the import from other countries.
- B.canis is not an OIE listed disease, but it is notifiable in some countries (and not others making tracking across borders difficult).
- Often reported in the national zoonoses reports.
- However it's difficult to diagnose because of the symptoms and issues with reliability of tests.
- This also makes outbreaks difficult to trace.
- Data on human cases not well documented.
- Information from questions:
 - Is this an inevitable by-product of free movement of pets?
 - Similar rise in cases of B.canis in the UK.
 - Many cases linked to import.
 - Often lack of cooperation from pet owners to disclose information about B.canis.
 - Similar increase in cases in Italy including one very large outbreak.

What next...

- Meeting widely seen as very valuable.
- Informal format adds particular value as a free space for talking about country trends.
- Issues about data sharing, concern that some sensitive information may leak if there aren't rules in place for the work group.
- Raised needs for a terms of reference.
- Widely accepted that disease-specific workshops would be useful.
- Raised needs for a descriptive name/banner to refer to work-group.

Appendix 3.

COHESIVE informal signal sharing meeting

Location: MS Teams

Date: 15/12/2021

Time: 09:30 – 12:00 CET

Participants: Sandra Cavaco, Karin Nyberg, Elina Lahti, Kitty Maassen, Hannah Joan Jørgensen, Mats Lindblad, Gavin Watkins, Andrew Frost, John McGiven, Frits Vlaanderen, Rob Dewar, Adam Barclay, , Stefan Craus, Elisa Mancuso, Jolyon Medlock, Leigh Thorne, José Francisco Ruiz Fons, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Joke van der Giessen, , Robert Smith, Gillian Diesel, Elisabetta Di Felice, Giorgia Amatori, Guido Di Donato, Miriam Maas, Alexandra Septfons, Isabel García Fernandez de Mera, Eduardo de Freitas Costa

1. Agenda

9.30-9.45 Opening & short introduction of all participants (via menti.com)

9.45-10.45 One Health risks of kept rats (pet rats, but also feeder rats for reptiles)

a. presentations

- Miriam Maas (RIVM, the Netherlands): Dutch situation with a focus on Seoul virus and leptospirosis.

- Elina Lahti (SVA, Sweden) & Rob Dewar (APHA, U.K.): short summary of the Swedish and U.K. situation

b. plenary discussion

Short break

10.45-11.45 One Health risks of Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever virus via within-EU-trade/importation of reservoir animals (such as horses) and/or vector ticks (*Hyalomma* sp.)

a. presentations

- Francisco Ruiz-Fons (UCLM, Spain): Spanish situation regarding *Hyalomma* ticks and CCHF virus

- Mathilde Uiterwijk (CMV NVWA, the Netherlands): Dutch situation regarding *Hyalomma* ticks and CCHF virus risks

b. plenary discussion

11.45-12.00 Terms of Reference (ToR)

The concept-ToR will be discussed. ToR contains ground rules about confidentiality, aims and responsibilities and other topics.

1.1. Notes

Miriam Maas – *SEOV and other zoonotic pathogens in kept rats, the Netherlands*

See presentation

Elina Lahti & Rob Dewar – *zoonotic pathogens in kept rats, Sweden & U.K.*

See presentation.

Discussion:

Especially young rats/mice are at risk for *Salmonella* infection.

In all countries, the outbreaks of SEOV, Salmonella and other zoonotic pathogens in kept rats (or mice) showed problems regarding:

- legal issues; responsibilities unclear, interpretation of legislation unclear, unclear what measures can be imposed
- traceability: owners and breeders are unknown [no registration in place], importers not well registered
- preventive measures for the owners/breeders. In the Netherlands for example, it was shown that the protective measures that were advised (personal protection, hygiene etc.) were abandoned quickly.

In Sweden, municipalities are responsible for outbreaks in pet animals.

Pet shops are registered, but not the breeders and individual rat owners.
 In the Netherlands it is estimated that 30.000 to 100.000 fresh feeder rats/mice are fed to reptiles each week, and around a million if frozen rats/mice are included.
 In the UK, there are also outbreaks of Hepatitis E related to kept rats/mice.
 'Fancy rats'; rats that are kept for shows. In all countries, cooperation of the rat owners regarding prevention and handling the outbreak is voluntary. The cooperation of fancy rat owners in UK was good. In the UK, several importers were active, now there is only one which has improved traceability a lot. The importer sends feeder mice/rats to the reptile owners once every 10 days. These mice/rats are now classified as raw pet food, so rules and measures are accordingly. Guidance has been published. Contaminated lines can only be sold when additional information & measures are implemented, or can be recalled.
 The transmission routes from reptiles or feeder rats/mice to people are complex. Especially children were *Salmonella* infected in the UK. Children are more at risk partly because of their behaviour towards reptiles (cuddling etc.) and less hygienic. Via social media children and their parents were informed about the risk of *Salmonella* and how to prevent infection. Instructions for reptile owners: [Advice to reptile owners following withdrawal and recall of frozen mice used as food for pets linked to Salmonella outbreak in people | Food Standards Agency](#)
 Patients were infected via direct contact with reptiles (that shed *Salmonella* by having been fed infected rats/mice), but also without direct contact; for example by having contact with contaminated materials, some patients did not even have reptiles in their household. The *Salmonella* seems to be present long after starting to feed *Salmonella* free rats/mice to the reptiles.
 The UK Salmonella outbreak > 10 years ago originated from feed rodents that were imported from U.S.

Francisco Ruiz-Fons (UCLM, Spain): Spanish situation regarding *Hyalomma* ticks and CCHF virus
 See presentation

Mathilde Uiterwijk (CMV NVWA, the Netherlands): Dutch situation regarding *Hyalomma* ticks and CCHF virus risks
 See presentation
 Discussion:

In 2016 the first patient was diagnosed with Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever virus in Spain. Already in 2010, CCHFv was found in wildlife (red deer) and *Hyalomma lusitanicum* ticks in Spain. *Hyalomma lusitanicum* is the most prevalent and widespread *Hyalomma* tick in Spain, and is primarily involved in the CCHFv circulation in Spain. Guidelines have been published in which information for professionals and people at risk are summarised.

Hosts of immature stadia of *H. lusitanicum* are also large ungulates. Birds are hosts of immature stadia of *H. marginatum* and *H. rufipes*, so these species can be imported to northern countries by migratory birds. The risk of importation of CCHFv via *H. marginatum* / *H. rufipes* from Spain seems to be low.

No *H. lusitanicum* in Italy, *H. marginatum* is endemic. Seroprevalence studies in wildlife and tick surveys are done to assess CCHFv.

2. Menti Questions & Answers

- Welcome to the European One Health platform for low-threshold sharing of zoonotic signal.
 Please enter your Name, Institute, Country and Area of work:

Rob Dewar, APHA, Risk Analysis
Joke van der Giessen, RIVM, NL
Jolyon Medlock, Head of Medical Entomology, UK Health Security Agency. Work on vector-borne disease (tick and mosquito-borne disease)
Andrew Frost, Animal and Plant Health Agency, UK, veterinary adviser working in One Health
Robert Smith, Public Health Wales, Wales, UK. Zoonoses, Gastrointestinal and Emerging Infections
Miriam Maas, RIVM, Netherlands, wildlife zoonoses
Kitty Maassen, RIVM, NL, emerging zoonoses
Frits Vlaanderen (RIVM)

Mathilde Uiterwijk, Centre for Monitoring of Vectors, NVWA, the Netherlands
Gillian Diesel, APHA, UK, Small animal disease surveillance
Septfons Alexandra, Santé publique France, Surveillance of zoonosis and vector-borne diseases
Elina Lahti, SVA (Sweden), Zoonoses
Elisa Mancuso, CESME (National Reference Centre for Exotic Diseases), Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Abruzzo e Molise - ITALY Vector-borne viral zoonoses
Francisco Ruiz-Fons, Spanish National Research Council - Spanish Game and Wildlife Research Institute, Spain. Veterinary Epidemiologist.
Stefan Craus - Veterinary Advisor, OCVO, Welsh Government
Isabel García Fernandez de Mera IREC Spain Tick borne diseases (UCLM-CSIC)
Eduardo de Freitas Costa, Wageningen Bioveterinary Institute, Netherlands
Leigh Thorne, APHA, Scientist Zoonotic Diseases
Guido Di Donato, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise, Italy
Alejandro, Spain, Zoonoses and Animal Health
Sandra Cavaco, INIAV, Portugal, Animal Health, zoonoses
Elisabetta Di Felice, IZS Abruzzo e Molise, Italia
Giorgia Amatori, IZS Abruzzo e Molise, Italia
Adam Barclay APHA Weybridge Zoonosis Field Investigation Team
Hannah Joan Jørgensen Norwegian Veterinary Institute

2. Is SEOV present in your country?

3. Which zoonoses are present in your country in relation to kept rats?

4. Do you think import of horses and other ungulates (from within EU) is a risk factor for introducing CCHFv into your country?

5. Do you have insight into how many horses and other ungulates are imported from other EU countries?

regarding wild ungulates, many of them are translocated for game purposes from Eastern Europe to many regions of Spain
Keeping information ongoing
No
No, I don't know
No, I don't know
I have no idea
Our International Trade Centre will have this information
No, only estimates.
No
No
Unsure
NI
Sort of
no

6. How do you think spreading of CCHFv can be prevented?

among others, tick surveillance

among others, tick surveillance
Entomological surveillance (tick birds also). Entomological and serological surveillance of introduced animal from other countries
Difficult to stop Hyalomma spreading. Raising awareness of their movement on birds and rapid alerting when they are found on horses/cattle/humans is important. Dogs should be treated prior to travel to prevent other Hyalommas (lusitanicum) being move
Not sure
Entomological and serological surveillance
entomological and serological surveillance
Control of ungulates movements and trying to control tick populations
I am not familiar with this infection
Tick control
Entomological surveillance
Entomological and serological surveillance of imported animals
See
unknown

7. What is a good way to communicate and share documents?

8. Do you have suggestions/remarks? Name of the working group, suggestions for ToR, length of the meeting, set up of the meeting etc.

no comments
No suggestions
I don't know
I don't know
I'm participating for the first time, so I have no suggestion yet!
One hour meetings as standard longer if exception dictates
On-line meetings are great, more likely to be able to attend.
Length of 2.5-3 h ideal if virtual meetings
Need more time to suggest a name. Tor looks good
2.5 hrs max, ideally 2.0hr. ToR look OK, no name as yet
no suggestions

9. Do you have suggestions for a theme or topic to be discussed during a next meeting?

Emerging tick-borne encephalitis

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
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Portuguese situation regarding CCHFv
Epidemiological situation of CCHF and update of diagnostical method (does exist SN safety method?)
diagnostic methods for CCHF (like safety SN, WGS)
Co-ordinated control strategy across Europe
Other vector-borne diseases, tbe, babesiosis, anaplasma
no
Import or travelling of dogs
Leptospirosis
Cryptosporidiosis
no suggestions
Epidemiology and diagnostic methods of CCHF

10. Enter your name & email address if you want to be part of the group

These answers are administered.